

THE ROLE OF GYMNASTICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MOVEMENT COORDINATION IN CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE

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Annotation

This proverb sees the role and problems of gymnastics in the development of coordination of movement in children of preschool age

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Coordination is the connection of movements in each part of the body. Separate movements become a whole movement, forming a clear, plastic and non-stressful movement. Body, head, arm and leg exercises are performed in three different planes relative to the body: straight, sideways and horizontal. Arm and leg movements: simultaneous movement (for example, turning both arms and legs to the right side at the same time); in different directions (for example, when jumping, the right hand and left leg rise).

Leg and arm movements are as follows: performed simultaneously (for example, while lying on the back, raising and lowering both legs); taking turns (for example, standing with hands on hips, standing on each leg in turn); successively, the movement is performed sequentially (for example, while standing, turning around with the hands in one place, and at the same time restoring the right hand, and turning the left hand down, then the opposite state, i.e. It's like chasing each other. It's best to combine exercises that focus on one side at a time. The most difficult for children in these exercises are the exercises that are performed in turn, so these exercises can be performed by older children of preschool age. All this improves coordination directed to improve.

The speed, difficulty and variety of movement are of great importance in the development of coordination. Action coordination cannot be imagined without the goal of openness. In the process of training, they are served by the surrounding people and the teacher's order as a goal.

To develop good aim in children, the following exercises are recommended:

- performing hand exercises, because the hands are the organs closest to the eyes (resting the hands forward, shaking them)

- playing the hands in a partially visible place, i.e. playing facing up or down.
- Moving the body forward, sideways, horizontally.
- Moving the legs back and to the sides.

The study of obtaining a temporary goal is carried out in the following way: Exercises performed under the command given by the teacher (for example, "sit", "straighten"; to the side, straight and other commands).

Exercise to music.

Exercises that are performed together with exercises to music (for example, "spread one's hands", "two-hands down") or another movement that does not take place in the same plane. Familiar exercises are performed independently after the command.

Dexterity in children can be developed through the following exercises:

Exercises that change the position quickly (for example, moving from a sitting position with legs outstretched to a back or lying position on the stomach, rotating around one's own axis while sitting).

Exercises that require mutual agreement (for example, exercises performed by two people, sitting opposite each other).

Exercises performed with some objects (ball, rope). Speed training depends on coordination and complex exercises. Complex fast movements develop children's motor skills well, but since these exercises are very difficult, they should be adapted to children, otherwise the child's body may be strained. It is impossible to develop coordination and dexterity without balance. Equilibrium is the center of gravity of a body resting on a plane.

To learn to maintain balance, the following exercises should be performed:

- standing on one end with legs close to each other and sitting with a straight back;
- standing on one leg and lifting the other forward. It is necessary to alternate legs;
- standing on one leg while closing the eyes; keeping the recovered leg in the air with closed eyes.

Rotations (jumping into a trap and spinning out of it; spinning around its own axis while standing and stopping; the same position but to the other side) reducing the base area (standing on a cube, sitting flat; standing on buruses, straightening one leg standing on one leg) What should an adult follow when exercising with children? It is necessary to exercise regularly, because the child should learn physical exercises and other movement skills well, and they should

have a good effect on physical development and health. necessary. A very important rule is to gradually increase the load during exercises.

In order for physical culture to give a cheerful mood, physical exercises and games should be chosen according to each child. For example, it is necessary to show exercises that imitate the lower class groups more. Exercises should be explained to the child in such a way that he understands the purpose of the actions. Tasks should be clear and understandable. It is necessary to make the child interested in exercises, to arouse the desire to actively move in it. Praise the child when he does the exercises well. We have recommended gymnastics exercises for children from 1 to 3 years below.

It is necessary to choose a physical activity based on the child's strength, physical fitness, and current health. How to increase or decrease the physical load according to the duration of the training, the appropriate starting position (lying down, sitting, standing), the number of repetitions of the exercises, their speed, amplitude, i.e. the range of movements can be changed with Physical stress can be reduced by alternating exercise with rest and breathing exercises.

The speed of movements should be moderate and slow, and they should be required to perform the exercises accurately. Horny children need to play calm, non-exciting games. After 4-8 days, it is necessary to replace some activities with new ones for children of preschool age. If this is not done, children will not be interested in training. It is also not recommended to change classes too often, because in doing so, the child cannot remember the classes well, and cannot learn one or another movement skills.

At the age of preschool education, the activity of the cortex of the large hemispheres of the brain becomes complicated. A 5-year-old child pronounces all letters and words clearly, composes long sentences easily, tells what he sees and hears.

During this period, the child begins to actively compare facts, analyze events, and improves memory. He is curious about everything and asks the big man countless questions and demands that he answer them. The period of asking the question "why" begins. An adult should answer her questions simply and calmly, listen to her patiently, and correct her if she says something wrong. At the same time, the child's brain should not be overtired with new impressions and concepts.

Do not read books to the child, especially books that are not suitable for his age, and do not take him to the movies or watch TV shows every day, because all these things can affect the development of the nervous system. is a trigger, and

in some cases it leads to the deterioration of speech (even to stuttering), inability to sleep well, decreased appetite, increased child excitability, and sometimes involuntary twitching or flying of muscles. At this age, the work of the organs of intuition, feeling, smell, cognition, sight, and hearing improves.

The child correctly expresses his feelings with words. If the eye is strained for a long time (looking at pictures in an uncomfortable position on a poorly lit table), the child's eye muscles are very tired, because the eye muscles are forced to change the shape of the pupil to adapt to good vision. This can lead to the development of nearsightedness over time. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure that the child sits properly, that the place where he reads is well lit, especially when he sees books in the picture, when he paints, when he glues something, or when he sews something.

From the age of 3, a child should eat independently and observe the rules of etiquette and manners. Before eating, he should wash and wipe his hands with soap under the supervision of an adult, help to set the table, sit properly around the table, hold the spoon in the right hand, the bread in the left hand, it is necessary for him to eat calmly without spilling, after eating, wipe his mouth with a napkin, push the chair behind him to its place, thank an older person, help in cleaning the dishes. A child 5 years old and older can now put things on the table, clean the table after eating, wipe the napkin, put the chairs in their place, etc.

A child of preschool age likes to listen to other people's words, talk, communicate with adults. Parents are often overworked. When they return from work, they tell a lot of interesting things to the child, it is necessary to play noisy games with him.

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